

Appendix: Verifying Fairness in Quantum Machine Learning

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A Proof of Lemma 1

Proof. This mainly results from [1, Theorem 9.1]: for any $\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$

$$\text{tr}(|\rho - \sigma|) = \max_{\{M_i\}_i} \sum_i |\text{tr}(M_i^\dagger M_i(\rho - \sigma))|$$

where the maximization is over all quantum measurements $\{M_i\}_i$. We complete the proof by noting that $\{\sqrt{\mathcal{E}^\dagger(M_i^\dagger M_i)}\}_i$ is a measurement and

$$\text{tr}(M_i^\dagger M_i \mathcal{E}(\rho - \sigma)) = \text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(M_i^\dagger M_i)(\rho - \sigma)),$$

where \mathcal{E}^\dagger is the conjugate map of \mathcal{E} . □

B Proof of Theorem 1

Proof. We first prove the first claim. The “if” direction can be derived by the definition of (ε, δ) -fairness, K^* and Eq.(3) in the paper. Then we prove “only if” direction. By Theorem 3 in the paper, we have that there exists a pair of mutually orthogonal pure quantum states $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$ such that

$$d(\mathcal{A}(\psi), \mathcal{A}(\phi)) = K^* D(\psi, \phi).$$

Note that $D(\psi, \phi) = 1$ results from the orthogonality of ψ and ϕ , i.e., $\langle \psi | \phi \rangle = 0$. Given a quantum state σ , let

$$\rho_\psi = \varepsilon\psi + (1 - \varepsilon)\sigma \quad \rho_\phi = \varepsilon\phi + (1 - \varepsilon)\sigma.$$

Then $D(\rho_\psi, \rho_\phi) = \varepsilon$. Subsequently,

$$d(\mathcal{A}(\rho_\psi), \mathcal{A}(\rho_\phi)) = \varepsilon d(\mathcal{A}(\psi), \mathcal{A}(\phi)) = \varepsilon K^* D(\psi, \phi) = \varepsilon K^* \leq \delta.$$

The above inequality follows from the definition of (ε, δ) -fairness of \mathcal{A} .

Next, we prove the second claim. If the (ε, δ) -fairness fails, i.e., $\delta < K^* \varepsilon$, then for any quantum state σ , $D(\rho_\psi, \rho_\phi) = \varepsilon$ and

$$d(\mathcal{A}(\rho_\psi), \mathcal{A}(\rho_\phi)) = K^* \varepsilon D(\psi, \phi) = K^* \varepsilon > \delta.$$

So (ρ_ψ, ρ_ϕ) is a bias pair by Definition 2 in the paper. □

C Single Quantum Measurement Distinguishability

In this section, we aim to prove Theorem 3 in the paper by reducing it to a problem, called *single quantum measurement distinguishability*.

Table 1: Quantum Distinguishability Problems Summary

Types Scenario	States	Super-operators	Multiple Measurements	Single Measurement
Prior Known	two states	two super-operators	two measurements	one measurement
Aims	one measurement	one protocol	one state	two states

The distinguishability of quantum data and computation models is a fundamental problem in the field of quantum information and has been intensively studied in the last two decades. For two prior known quantum states (super-operators), *quantum states (super-operators) distinguishability* mainly considers to find an optimal measurement (protocol) to determine which one is given through (a sequence of) measurement outcomes [1,2,3,4]. Besides this, *multiple quantum measurements distinguishability* [5,6] was also studied to find an optimal quantum state to distinguish two prior known quantum measurements in a similar scenario. See Table 1 for the summary. A fundamental step of these distinguishability problems is to compute the maximum probability $\Pr(\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}} | \rho, \sigma)$ of discriminating two quantum states ρ and σ by measurement $\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$. More specifically, suppose that Alice is randomly given a state X from two prior known quantum states $\{\rho, \sigma\}$, and she wishes to use a quantum measurement $\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$ to guess whether X is state ρ or state σ . The best strategy (successful probability) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pr(\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}} | \rho, \sigma) &= \frac{1}{2} \Pr(i \in A | X = \rho) + \frac{1}{2} \Pr(i \notin A | X = \sigma) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in A} \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \rho) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \notin A} \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \sigma) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \max\{\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \rho), \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \sigma)\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \left[\frac{\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho + \sigma))}{2} + \frac{|\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))|}{2} \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))|
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{M}_i = M_i^\dagger M_i$ for all $i \in \mathcal{O}$, and $A = \{i \in \mathcal{O} \mid \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \rho) \geq \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \sigma)\}$ records the set of outcomes that the measurement probability of ρ is higher than

or equal to that of σ . In the context of quantum distinguishability, as we only consider the probabilities of measurement outcomes, in the following, we use *positive operator-valued measurement (POVM)* $\{\mathcal{M}_i = M_i^\dagger M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$ to replace general measurement $\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$. A POVM is used when we do not care the post-measurement states [1, Section 2.2.6].

In the context of quantum states distinguishability, Alice further tries to select a different measurement to optimize the probability $\Pr(\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}|\rho, \sigma)$, i.e.,

$$\max_{\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}} \Pr(\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}|\rho, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \max_{\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))| = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} D(\rho, \sigma).$$

The last equation results from [1, Theorem 9.1]. Thus, the trace distance of ρ and σ represents quantum states distinguishability.

In this paper, we treat ρ and σ as variables to maximize $\Pr(\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}|\rho, \sigma)$ which is the problem of *single quantum measurement distinguishability* (See the last column of Table 1). More specifically, Alice seeks to use measurement $\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$ to maximize the probability that her guess is correct by selecting different candidate pair of quantum states (ρ, σ) . That is

$$\max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \Pr(\{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}|\rho, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))|.$$

As we can see, $\frac{1}{2} \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))|$ characterizes single quantum measurement distinguishability. Interestingly, it is the same to the Lipschitz constant K^* of quantum decision model $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{E}, \{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$ when $\mathcal{E} = \text{id}_{\mathcal{H}}$, the identity super-operator on \mathcal{H} : $\text{id}_{\mathcal{H}}(\rho) = \rho$ for all $\rho \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$.

Lemma 1. *Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{E}, \{M_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$ be a quantum decision model and K^* the Lipschitz constant of \mathcal{A} . Then*

$$2K^* = \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))| = \max_{\rho \perp \sigma} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))|,$$

where $\mathcal{M}_i = M_i^\dagger M_i$ for all $i \in \mathcal{O}$ and $\rho \perp \sigma$ means that ρ is orthogonal to σ , i.e., $\text{tr}(\rho\sigma) = 0$.

Proof. First of all, by Eq. (3) in the paper,

$$K^* = \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \frac{d(\mathcal{A}(\rho), \mathcal{A}(\sigma))}{D(\rho, \sigma)} = \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))|}{\text{tr}(|\rho - \sigma|)}.$$

For any $\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$, let $\rho - \sigma = \Delta_+ - \Delta_-$ be a decomposition into orthogonal positive and negative parts (i.e., $\Delta_\pm \geq 0$ and $\Delta_+ \Delta_- = 0$). Then we have $\text{tr}(\Delta_+) = \text{tr}(\Delta_-)$ and $\text{tr}(|\rho - \sigma|) = 2\text{tr}(\Delta_+)$. Subsequently,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))|}{\text{tr}(|\rho - \sigma|)} &= \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\Delta_+ - \Delta_-))|}{2\text{tr}(\Delta_+)} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \left| \text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i) \frac{\Delta_+}{\text{tr}(\Delta_+)} - \mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i) \frac{\Delta_-}{\text{tr}(\Delta_-)}) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

As $\frac{\Delta_{\pm}}{\text{tr}(\Delta_{\pm})} \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$ are two orthogonal quantum states, we can obtain that

$$2K^* = \max_{\rho \perp \sigma} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))|.$$

Next, we prove

$$\max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))| = \max_{\rho \perp \sigma} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))|.$$

The r.h.s is certainly a lower bound of the l.h.s since any two orthogonal quantum states are in $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$. So we have to show that it is also an upper bound. Again, for any $\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$, let $\rho - \sigma = \Delta_+ - \Delta_-$ be a decomposition into orthogonal positive and negative parts. Then we have

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))| = \text{tr}(\Delta_+) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \left| \text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i) \frac{\Delta_+}{\text{tr}(\Delta_+)} - \mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i) \frac{\Delta_-}{\text{tr}(\Delta_-)}) \right|.$$

As trace distance is in $[0, 1]$ and $D(\rho, \sigma) = \text{tr}(\Delta_+)$, $\text{tr}(\Delta_+) \leq 1$. Therefore,

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))| \leq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \left| \text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i) \frac{\Delta_+}{\text{tr}(\Delta_+)} - \mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i) \frac{\Delta_-}{\text{tr}(\Delta_-)}) \right|.$$

We complete the proof by noting that $\frac{\Delta_{\pm}}{\text{tr}(\Delta_{\pm})} \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$ are two orthogonal quantum states. \square

By the above lemma, we can see that the distinguishability of a POVM $\{\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$ is $\frac{1}{2}(1 + K^*)$. Furthermore, it is worth noting that $\{\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)\}$ can be any POVM as \mathcal{E} can be the identity super-operator $\text{id}_{\mathcal{H}}$ on \mathcal{H} . Thus K^* represents the distinguishability of quantum POVM and mathematically can be redefined as a mapping:

$$K^* : \mathbb{M} \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad K^*(\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) = \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))|$$

where \mathbb{M} denotes the set of all POVMs on \mathcal{H} .

Then, with the observation that $K^*(\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) = K^*(\{U\mathcal{M}_iU^\dagger\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$ for all unitary matrix U , we can restate Theorem 2 in the paper in the context of single quantum measurement distinguishability as follows.

Theorem 1. *For any POVM $\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$ and super-operator \mathcal{E} , we have*

$$K^*(\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) \geq K^*(\{\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}).$$

Proof. By definition of $K^*(\cdot)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
K^*({\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) &= \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathcal{M}_i)(\rho - \sigma))| \\
&= \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\mathcal{E}(\rho) - \mathcal{E}(\sigma)))| \\
&\leq \max_{\rho, \sigma \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\rho - \sigma))| \\
&= K^*({\mathcal{M}_i}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}).
\end{aligned}$$

The above inequality comes from $\{\mathcal{E}(\rho) : \rho \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})\} \subseteq \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$. \square

In the following, for completing the proof of Theorem 3 in the paper, we show how to compute $K^*({\mathcal{M}_i}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$ for any POVM $\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$.

First, we observe that the optimization problem of computing $K^*({\mathcal{M}_i}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$ in Lemma 1 can be constrained in pure states instead of searching mixed states.

Lemma 2.

$$2K^*({\mathcal{M}_i}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) = \max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi - \phi))|,$$

where $|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle$ means that $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$ are mutually orthogonal, i.e., $\langle \psi | \phi \rangle = 0$, and $\psi = |\psi\rangle\langle \psi|$ and $\phi = |\phi\rangle\langle \phi|$.

Proof. The r.h.s is certainly a lower bound of the l.h.s since the set of pure states is a subset of $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H})$. So we have to show that it is also an upper bound. To this end, for any orthogonal $\rho \perp \sigma$, there is a probability distribution $\{p_j\}_j$ and two sets of pure states $\{|\phi_j\rangle\}_j$ and $\{|\psi_j\rangle\}_j$ such that $\rho - \sigma$ has a convex decomposition:

$$\rho - \sigma = \sum_j p_j(\psi_j - \phi_j).$$

Then by the triangle inequality, we have

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \rho - \mathcal{M}_i \sigma)| \leq \max_j \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi_j - \phi_j))|.$$

Furthermore, since for any j , $|\psi_j\rangle \perp |\phi_j\rangle$, we can claim that

$$\max_j \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi_j - \phi_j))| \leq \max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi - \phi))|.$$

\square

Theorem 2.

$$K^*({\mathcal{M}_i}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) = \max_{A \subseteq \mathcal{O}} [\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A) - \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)]$$

where $\mathcal{M}_A = \sum_{i \in A} \mathcal{M}_i$, and $\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A)$ and $\lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)$ are the maximum and minimum eigenvalues of positive semi-definite matrix \mathcal{M}_A , respectively.

Furthermore, let $A^* \subseteq \mathcal{O}$ be an optimal solution of reaching $K^*(\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$, i.e.,

$$A^* = \arg \max_{A \subseteq \mathcal{O}} [\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A) - \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)]$$

and $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$ be two normalized eigenvectors corresponding to the maximum and minimum eigenvalues of \mathcal{M}_{A^*} , respectively. Then we have

$$2K^*(\{\mathcal{M}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi - \phi))|,$$

where $\psi = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ and $\phi = |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, we have to show

$$\max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi - \phi))| = 2 \max_{A \subseteq \mathcal{O}} [\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A) - \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)].$$

First, we claim that the l.h.s is an upper bound of the r.h.s. For any subset $A \subseteq \mathcal{O}$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi - \phi))| \\ & \geq \max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} [|\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_A(\psi - \phi))| + |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_{\mathcal{O} \setminus A}(\psi - \phi))|] \\ & = 2 \max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_A(\psi - \phi))| \\ & = 2 \max_{|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle} \langle \psi | \mathcal{M}_A | \psi \rangle - \langle \phi | \mathcal{M}_A | \phi \rangle \\ & = 2[\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A) - \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)]. \end{aligned}$$

The above inequality results from the triangle inequality, the first equality is obtained by $\mathcal{M}_A = I - \mathcal{M}_{\mathcal{O} \setminus A}$, and the last equality follows the linear algebra fact: for any positive semi-definite matrix \mathcal{M} ,

$$\max_{|\psi\rangle} \langle \psi | \mathcal{M} | \psi \rangle = \lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}) \quad \min_{|\phi\rangle} \langle \phi | \mathcal{M} | \phi \rangle = \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M})$$

and the optimal $|\psi^*\rangle$ and $|\phi^*\rangle$ are corresponding to maximum and minimum normalized eigenvectors, respectively; furthermore, if $\lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}) \neq \lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M})$, then $|\psi^*\rangle \perp |\phi^*\rangle$, otherwise $\mathcal{M} = kI$ for some constant $k > 0$ and any two orthogonal pure states in \mathcal{H} are the optimal $|\psi^*\rangle$ and $|\phi^*\rangle$.

Next, we prove the l.h.s is also a lower bound. Let $A = \{i \in \mathcal{O} \mid \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \psi) \geq \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i \phi)\}$. For any $|\psi\rangle \perp |\phi\rangle$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_i |\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_i(\psi - \phi))| \\ & = \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_A(\psi - \phi)) - \text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_{\mathcal{O} \setminus A}(\psi - \phi)) \\ & = 2\text{tr}(\mathcal{M}_A(\psi - \phi)) \\ & \leq 2[\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A) - \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)] \\ & \leq 2 \max_{A \subseteq \mathcal{O}} [\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{M}_A) - \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{M}_A)]. \end{aligned}$$

The first equality comes from the definition of set A , the second one is obtained by $\mathcal{M}_A = I - \mathcal{M}_{\mathcal{O}\setminus A}$, and the first inequality is observed by the above linear algebra fact. \square

Now we are ready to prove Theorem 3 in the paper.

Proof. This directly results from Theorem 2 for $K^*(\{\mathcal{E}^\dagger(M_i^\dagger M_i)\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}})$ with POVM $\{\mathcal{E}^\dagger(M_i^\dagger M_i)\}_{i \in \mathcal{O}}$. \square

D More Scalability Experiments

Table 2 summarizes the experimental results for computing the Lipschitz constant K^* on 29-qubit QCNN models by Algorithm 1 in the paper. In this experiment, the time-out (TO) is set as 10 hours.

Table 2: Experimental results of Lipschitz constant K^* of QCNN models.

#Qubits	Noise		Evaluation I		Evaluation II		Evaluation III	
	type	probability	K^*	Time	K^*	Time	K^*	Time
29	None		1.0000	\	1.0000	\	1.0000	\
	Phase flip	10^{-4}	0.9999	25.46m	0.9999	17.43m	0.9999	1.24h
		10^{-3}	0.9982	28.38m	0.9983	17.51m	0.9978	57.38m
		10^{-2}	-	TO	-	TO	-	TO
	Depolarize	10^{-4}	0.9998	22.71m	0.9998	45.08m	0.9997	34.94m
		10^{-3}	0.9985	41.53m	0.9978	33.45m	0.9978	35.64m
		10^{-2}	-	TO	0.9773	1.76h	0.9810	1.47h
	Bit flip	10^{-4}	0.9998	33.60m	0.9999	54.64m	0.9998	1.06h
		10^{-3}	0.9978	55.11m	0.9974	1.33h	0.9977	40.71m
		10^{-2}	-	TO	-	TO	-	TO
	Mixed noise	10^{-4}	0.9998	35.4m	0.9998	24.10m	0.9998	36.89m
		10^{-3}	0.9986	20.33m	0.9977	26.83m	0.9980	28.05m
		10^{-2}	0.9778	4.74h	-	TO	0.9851	32.45m

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